

Chief Executive Office Characteristics Effect on Financial Reporting Quality in Vietnam: The Moderating Role of Firm Size

Nga, Tran Thi Nguyet

School of Finance and Accounting, Industrial University of Ho Chi Minh City, Hochiminh City, Vietnam

Faculty of Accounting and Auditing, University of Finance - Marketing, Hochiminh City, Vietnam

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7145-1663>

***Diem, Ngo Nhat Phuong**

Faculty of Accounting and Auditing, University of Finance - Marketing, Hochiminh City, Vietnam. Email: ngodiem@ufm.edu.vn.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0145-8000>.

*** Corresponding author: Diem, Ngo Nhat Phuong**

Abstract

Background: Research on financial reporting quality and the impact of Chief Executive Office (CEO) on financial reporting quality is an issue of interest to academics.

Objective: The study aims to assess the impact of the CEO composite index on financial reporting quality (FRQ) and examine the moderating role of firm size on the relationship between the CEO and financial reporting quality in listed companies in Vietnam.

Methodology: The study uses a data sample of 459 Vietnamese listed companies in the period 2016 to 2023, through Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) regression with the dependent variable representing the quality of financial statements measured by the E Score model.

Result: This result shows that the CEO representative composite factor has a significant impact on the FRQ of the enterprise. In addition, the study also found the moderating role of firm size (FS) in the relationship between CEO and FRQ.

Conclusion: The more positive characteristics that a CEO possesses, the more likely they are to enhance FRQ. In addition, FS plays a positive moderating role in the relationship between CEO and FRQ in listed firms in Vietnam.

Unique contributions: This study has contributed to the understanding of the significant positive impact of CEO on FRQ in listed companies in Vietnam. This study also demonstrated the essential role of FS in improving FRQ and controlling CEO behaviour.

Key Recommendations: Future studies should examine other factors on CEOs, to explore in more detail FRQ in the Vietnamese market.

Keywords: Chief Executive Officer (CEO); Firm Size (FS); Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ), Vietnam

Introduction

Financial statements provide information to various stakeholders (Solikhah et al., 2022). The accounting information in financial reports plays an important role in supporting the management and operation of enterprises. Therefore, high-quality financial statements are crucial for users of financial statement information. FRQ is measured in a variety of ways, including through earnings management behavior (Bouaziz et al., 2020) or through the reflection of earnings information (Asyik et al., 2023). CEO is the head of the management apparatus, responsible for implementing the company's development strategy and making key decisions related to finance, human resources, production, and business operations. The CEO also possesses sufficient authority to intervene in the information presented in financial reports (Bouaziz et al., 2020).

Currently, numerous studies worldwide have examined the impact of individual CEO characteristics—such as gender, age, dual roles, nationality, income, stock ownership ratio, meeting frequency, and financial expertise on FRQ (Habib & Hossain, 2013; Bouaziz et al., 2020; Qawasmeh & Azzam, 2020; Huang et al., 2012). However, the findings across these studies remain inconsistent. For instance, CEO income was found to influence FRQ in the research by Habib and Hossain (2013) but showed no impact in studies by Bouaziz et al. (2020). Similarly, some studies acknowledged that older CEOs improve FRQ (Huang et al., 2012), whereas Qawasmeh & Azzam (2020) argued that CEO age has no role in earnings management and, consequently, no impact on FRQ. Regarding CEO duality roles, some studies suggested that CEOs who also serve as board chairs reduce FRQ (Feng et al., 2011), while Bouaziz et al. (2020) found a positive correlation between CEO dual roles and FRQ. The inconsistent results of these studies on individual CEO characteristics indicate the need for research that synthesizes these factors into a composite variable representing the CEO's influence on FRQ.

FS is an attribute that influences FRQ (Dechow & Ge, 2006). Large-scale enterprises are often expected to have a well-structured accounting system with effective internal controls to ensure transparency and accuracy in financial reporting. Additionally, with strong financial capabilities, large companies can afford to hire accounting, auditing, and financial consulting experts, thereby improving FRQ and enhancing compliance with international accounting standards (Chalaki et al., 2012). Moreover, as enterprises expand in scale, management complexity increases, leading to a rise in agency problems between shareholders and the board of directors. This necessitates the implementation of effective corporate governance mechanisms to minimize conflicts of interest, enhance accountability, and protect stakeholders' rights (Solikhah et al., 2022). Furthermore, the FS also has a significant impact on the levels of earnings management (EM)—one of the important ways to measure the FRQ. Many previous studies have shown that there is a close link between FS and EM, however, the research results are not completely consistent. Specifically, some studies such as Nalarreason and Mardiati (2019), as well as Ruwanti et al. (2019) have concluded that the size of the company has a significant positive relationship with EM. This means that the larger the company, the higher the level of EM due to pressure from regulatory agencies, investor supervision and financial transparency requirements. On the contrary, some other studies such as Hessayri and Saihi (2015) and Abbadi et al. (2016) came to the opposite conclusion, suggesting that there is a

significant negative relationship between FS and EM. Therefore, this study not only focuses on the relationship between CEO and FRQ but also examines the moderating role of FS in this relationship.

This study makes several contributions to the existing theory as follows. First, we add to the existing evidence on the impact of the composite factor representing the CEO on FRQ, without considering individual factors, in listed companies in Vietnam. Secondly, the study provides further clarification on how the CEO can influence FRQ through the moderating role of firm size. Thirdly, to measure FRQ, the study uses the FSCORE index of Nguyen et al. (2022). This is the first study to apply these indicators to assess FRQ in Vietnam - a developing country with an economy in transition and belonging to the frontier market group.

The structure of the article consists of six sections. In addition to the introduction, the next section presents research theories. Section 3 provides a theoretical background and hypotheses. Part 4 is the methodology. Section 5 provides the research results and the final section presents conclusions with policy implications.

Research theory

This study applies and combines various theories to build a comprehensive analytical framework to explain the impact of the CEO on the FRQ of publicly traded companies in Vietnam. The agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) examines the relationship between owners and agents (specifically CEOs). Corporate governance enables owners to monitor the behavior and business activities of agents. Therefore, it is essential to establish a system that effectively and appropriately supervises agents' activities to protect owners' interests and reduce earnings management behavior, thereby improving FRQ. In large companies, the separation between ownership and management is more distinct, leading to a higher risk of conflicts of interest between shareholders and managers. As a result, monitoring mechanisms (e.g., auditing, rewards, and penalties) need to be strengthened to enhance FRQ, which in turn leads to higher agency costs.

The upper echelons theory, one of the important foundations in the field of strategic management and organizational behavior and proposed by Hambrick and Mason (1984), this theory argues that CEOs' decision-making processes are influenced by how they interpret the strategic situations they encounter. This interpretation can be shaped by personal factors such as experience, personality, and other characteristics, which may lead to the risk of CEOs manipulating earnings, thereby affecting FRQ. With their shared responsibility for ensuring the company's performance, CEOs can indeed influence financial reporting.

Theoretical background and hypothesis development

Worldwide, studies on the characteristics of CEOs affecting FRQ have primarily been conducted in two main directions. First, there have been many studies on the impact of individual CEO characteristics on FRQ. Hrazdil et al. (2023) discovered evidence of better accrual quality in companies led by gender-diverse CEO/CFO pairs, in comparison to the accrual quality reported in companies led by all-male CEO/CFO pairs. Another study by Habib and Hossain (2013) explores

theories regarding the relationship between various aspects of CEO/CFO characteristics and the attributes of accounting information. The study focuses on three key issues: “the relationship between FRQ and CEO/CFO characteristics, the effect of managerial overconfidence on the results of financial reporting (FR), and the influence of CEO/CFO gender on FR outcomes”. In addition, Bouaziz et al. (2020) showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between CEO duality, CEO nationality and FRQ. However, no relationship was found between CEO compensation and EM. Furthermore, Qawasmeh and Azzam (2020) demonstrate that CEOs’ EM is higher in the early years of their careers than in later years, CEO ownership plays an important role in increasing the level of EM to maximize their compensation. However, the age and experience of CEOs do not play any role in increasing or decreasing the extent of discretionary accruals. Second, the study examines the composite factor representing the CEO's influence on FRQ, Nguyen et al. (2021) conducted research on CEO profiles and earnings quality. The study proposed a single measure to synthesize 9 different CEO characteristics that take the value of 1 or 0 and use them to signal earnings quality, the measure is named PSCORE. Higher PSCORE indicates lower earnings quality. Personal characteristics include: experience as CEO, experience as CFO, financial expertise, performance in the last 3 years of tenure, reputation in the early years as CEO, CEO concurrently serving as chairman of the board, CEO as founder or co-founder of the company, and CEO age.

Based on the above studies, this study will combine the individual characteristics of the CEO into a composite factor representing the CEO, including the individual variables: Previous work experience as a CFO; Professional qualifications related to finance; CEO is in the first three years of working at the company; CEO age; Performance in the last three years of the term; Gender, CEO is a foreigner, CEO rotation in the fiscal year. Based on the study's overview and perception, hypothesis H1 is suggested:

H₁: The CEO Representative composite factor has a negative impact on FRQ.

Empirical studies have shown that FS is one of the important moderating factors. The first view is that FS negatively affects FRQ, meaning that large firms tend to manipulate earnings more. For example, Wuryani (2012) found that large firms tend to engage in earnings manipulation more aggressively than small firms. Similarly, Türegün (2018) also found that large firms use EM more than small firms. In contrast, the second view suggests that FS is positively related to FRQ, as shown by Soyemi and Olawale (2019). Some other studies also show that large companies have advantages in terms of economies of scale and scope, making them less likely to engage in earnings manipulation (Peni & Vähämaa, 2010).

Meek et al. (2007) argue that large firms tend to have strong governance structures, lower levels of information asymmetry, and are subject to greater scrutiny from auditors and financial analysts, leading to less earnings management. Based on the above arguments, with the expectation that a large firm will improve the effectiveness of CEO monitoring, reduce earnings management, and improve FRQ, we propose a hypothesis:

H₂: FS positively moderates the relationship between CEO representative composite factor and FRQ.

In summary, building upon the prior findings and theoretical framework, the research model is formulated according to the following figure:

Figure 1: Proposed research model

Methodology

The sample and data for the research.

The data were collected from listed companies in Vietnam on two exchanges: the Hanoi Stock Exchange and the Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange, during the period from 2016 to 2023. The total includes 459 non-financial companies listed on the Vietnamese stock market (excluding financial companies), with 227 companies listed on the HOSE and 232 companies listed on the HNX across 12 industries. Companies were excluded from this study if they were listed after 2016 or if their financial data was incomplete during this period. These criteria were applied to maintain a strong, balanced, and relevant research data sample. In total, 459 listed companies with relevant data were included, corresponding to 3. 659 observations.

The Research Model

To assess the impact of CEO on FRQ and examine the moderating role of FS in this relationship, the following research models are proposed.

Model 1: $FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * CEOR_{it} + \beta_2 * LEV_{it} + \beta_3 * FAGE_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$

Model 2: $FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * CEOR_{it} + \beta_2 * CEORFS_{it} + \beta_3 * LEV_{it} + \beta_4 * FAGE_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$

In these models, FRQ is measured by the FCORE earnings management index of Nguyen et al. (2022).

Table 1 - Definitions and Measurements of Variables

Code	Variable	Formula	Reference
Dependent variable			
FRQ	Financial reporting quality	FCORE is a composite index of 15 individual signals that take a value of 1 (if earnings management is suspected) or 0 (otherwise). A	Nguyen et al. (2022)

		high value of FCORE suggests that the firm is likely to engage in EM, which reduces FRQ	
<p>FCORE = FSEO + FDDEBT + FMA + FOV + FROA + FDROA + FDIV + FDISTRESS + FDEBT + FSIZE + FCYCLE + FAUDIT + FBLOAT + FAPE + FBT</p> <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + FSEO: is one if the total shares issued and outstanding as of year t-end of a company increases by at least five percent compared to last year and there is positive proceeds from the issuance of common/preferred shares, otherwise it is zero. + FDEBT: is one if DEBT is five percent or higher (DEBT is calculated as the percentage change in total short-term and long-term debt compared to last year). Otherwise, it is zero + FMA: is one if a company announces an M&A deal during the fiscal year. Otherwise, it is zero + FOV: is one if $MB > MB^{80}_{k,t}$; otherwise, it is zero. (MB is the ratio of the market value to the book value of equity.); zero otherwise + FROA: is one if “earnings before special items divided by initial total assets-ROA” is equal to or greater than 0 but less than 0.01. Otherwise, it is zero. + FDROA: is one if “the change in ROA compared to last year” is equal to or greater than 0 but less than 0.005. Otherwise, it is zero + FDIV: is one if DIVDE is equal to or greater than 0, but less than 0.01. Otherwise, it is zero. (DIVDE is the gap between net earnings and overall cash dividends divided by total assets at the beginning of the period). + FDISTRESS: is one if ZCORE is negative. Otherwise, it is zero. <p>$Z_{core} = 1.2*A1 + 1.4*A2 + 3.3*A3 + 0.6*A4 + 1.0*A5$</p> <p>Trong đó:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A1 = WC/TA A2 = undistributed profit/TA A3 = EBIT/ TA A4 = The ratio of market capitalization to total debt (TD) A5 = Asset Performance <p>Note:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working capital (WC) = short-term Assets – Short-term debt. Asset Performance = Revenue/Total assets (TA). + FDEBT: is one if “the ratio of TD to TA” is lower than the corresponding $DEBT^{20}_{k,t}$; otherwise it is zero. + FSIZE: is one if MVE - initial market value of equity is smaller than the corresponding $MEV^{20}_{k,t}$; otherwise, it is zero. + FCYCLE: is one 1 if the company's operating cash flow is negative, financing cash flow is positive and investing cash flow is negative (construction phase) or operating and financing cash flow are positive while investing cash flow is negative (growth phase); otherwise, it is zero. + FAUDIT: is one if the company is not audited by Big 4. + FBLOAT: is one if the firm's initial NOA is smaller than the corresponding $NOA^{20}_{k,t}$; otherwise, it is zero. <p>(NOA – net operating assets, which is the sum of the net book value of equity plus total liabilities minus cash and cash equivalents, all over TA).</p>			

<p>+ FAPE: is one if the company's initial APE is smaller than the corresponding $APE^{20}_{k,t}$; otherwise, it is zero. (APE is the ratio of assets, plant and equipment divided by TA). + FBT: is one if BTAX is higher than the corresponding $BTAX^{20}_{k,t}$; otherwise, it is zero. (BTAX is the absolute value of the difference between pre-tax profit and estimated total taxable income).</p>			
Independent variables			
CEOR	CEO Representative Composite Factor	CEOR is a representative composite factor based on individual CEO factors affecting FRQ, including 8 individual factors, specifically explained below each individual factor. $CEOR = PCFO + PCERT + PEARLY + PFOUND + PAGE + PROA + PNATI + PTURN$	
PCFO	Previous work experience as a CFO	Is one if the CEO lacks experience as a CFO; otherwise it is zero.	Nguyen et al. (2021)
PCERT	Professional qualifications related to finance	Is one if the CEO does not hold an MBA or CPA equivalent; otherwise, it is zero.	Nguyen et al. (2021)
PEARLY	The CEO is in his first three years at the company	Is one if the CEO is within his or her first three years at the company; otherwise it is zero.	Nguyen et al. (2021)
PAGE	CEO age	Is one if the CEO is within one year of retirement age; otherwise, it is zero.	Nguyen et al. (2021)
PROA	Performance in the last 3 years of the term	Is one if the average return on assets (aveROA) over the last three years of the CEO's tenure is negative; otherwise it is zero	Nguyen et al. (2021)
PNATI	CEO Nationality	Is one if the CEO is a foreigner; otherwise it is zero.	Osazevaru (2022)
PTURN	CEO turnover	Is one if the company has CEO turnover during the fiscal year; zero otherwise.	Al-Faryan (2024)
Moderated variable			
CEORFS	Moderated variable of CEOR components and FS. It is conducted based on this formula: $CEORFS = CEOR * FS$		
FS	Firm size	Logarithm of Total Assets	Solikhah et al. (2022)
Control variables			
LEV	Financial leverage	$\frac{Total\ liabilities}{Total\ asset}$	Nguyen et al. (2021)
FAGE	Firm age	Current year minus year of establishment	Osazevaru (2022)

Source: Author's compilation.

Empirical result and discussions

Descriptive statistic

Table 2 - Summary Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
FCORE	3,659	3.657	1.358	0	9
CEOR	3,659	3.648	0.897	0	7
CEORFS	3,659	43.556	10.977	0	98.444
FAGE	3,659	1.400	0.229	0.477	1.982
LEV	3,659	-0.407	0.317	-3.231	0.112

Source: Research database using Stata 17

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics of the variables in the study, including dependent, independent, interaction, and control variables. The dependent variable, financial reporting quality, measured by the FCORE index, has an average value of 3.657, indicating that earnings management among listed companies in Vietnam during 2016–2023 is not excessively high, consistent with the findings of Nguyen et al. (2022). The composite factor representing CEOs has an average value of 3.648, reflecting significant differences among companies. The CEOR variable takes a value of 1 when the CEO lacks experience, does not hold a CPA-equivalent certification, or is within one year of retirement, increasing the likelihood of earnings management and reducing financial reporting quality. Finally, the interaction variable CEORFS has an average value of 43.556, with substantial variation among companies.

Correlation analysis and VIF values

Table 3 - Pearson correlations and VIF values.

Variable	FCORE	CEOR	CEORFS	FAGE	LEV	VIF
FCORE	1,000					
CEOR	0.055***	1,000				1.01
CEORFS	0.025	0.970***	1,000			
FAGE	-0.037**	-0.061***	-0.062***	1,000		1.01
LEV	-0.084***	-0.098***	-0.010	0.091***	1,000	1.02

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Research database using Stata 17

In Table 3, the correlation test results show that the absolute values of the correlation coefficients between pairs of variables are less than 0.5 (except for the correlation between CEOR and CEORFS, which is quite large but still less than 1), proving that the variables in the research model are not strongly correlated. At the same time, the table also presents the VIF coefficient, an important indicator to identify the possibility of multicollinearity in the model, the factor components in the research model give VIF coefficient < 2 , proving that the model does not have serious multicollinearity.

Model selection testing

Table 4 - Tests for Model Selection

The types of examination	Model 1	Model 2
F-test	4.53***	4.43***
Hausman	12.33***	20.03***
Heteroskedasticity	2.6e+08***	1.8e+07***
Wooldridge	28.34***	30.10***

Source: Research database using Stata 17

The data used in the study is panel data, therefore, to ensure high reliability in evaluating and selecting the appropriate model, the author conducted two important tests: F test and Hausman test. These two tests were performed to determine the most optimal model among three models: Pooled OLS, fixed effects model (FEM), and random effects model (REM). The test results presented in Table 4 show that the FEM model is the most suitable choice. After selecting the FEM model, the study continued to check for common technical problems in panel data, including heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation between variables. The test results show that the P value is less than 5%, which means that the FEM model has problems with heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. If not corrected, these phenomena can lead to inaccurate estimates and distort the analysis results. To deal with this problem, the author used the generalized least squares (GLS) estimation method, a method commonly applied in cases where data have heterogeneous error variance and autocorrelation. This method helps to adjust the error, improve the accuracy of the estimation, thereby enhancing the reliability of the research results. The regression results after applying the GLS model are presented in detail in Table 5.

Regression analysis results and discussion

Table 5 - Regression Estimation using GLS

Variable	Model 1	Model 2
CEOR	0.068***	0.802***
CEORFS		- 0.062***
FAGE	- 0.244**	- 0.237**
LEV	- 0.215***	- 0.057
Constant	3.619***	3.688***
Model information		
Wald chi2	26.80	75.58
Prob>chi2	0.0000	0.0000
Observations	3.659	3.659

Source: Research database using Stata 17

The first model (Table 5) shows that the higher the CEO composite index, the more EM behavior increases and the FRQ decreases, hypothesis H1 is accepted. This means that the closer the composite index is to 0, the more characteristics such as experience, expertise, ... the CEO has,

which increases the FRQ. This result is consistent with the study of Nguyen et al. (2021), when the CEO index increases, the presence of earnings manipulation also increases. This result is also consistent with the upper echelons theory, which suggests that CEOs with experience, expertise, no concurrent positions, no foreigners... will understand business activities, so the FRQ will increase.

The model 2, the interaction variable CEORFS has a negative impact on FCORE ($\beta_2 = -0.062$, $p < 0.01$), meaning that increasing FS may reduce the positive relationship between CEO and FCORE. This means that as the FS increases, the relationship between CEO and FRQ may increase (the higher the CEO, the lower FRQ in small-sized companies), H2 is accepted. This result is consistent with the research of Peni & Vähämaa (2010); Meek et al. (2007), which proves the essential role of FS in improving FRQ and controlling CEO behavior.

Conclusion

The study was conducted to examine the impact of the CEO representative composite factor on FRQ, and also analyze the moderating role of FS in the relationship between CEO and FRQ of listed companies in Vietnam in the period 2016-2023. The GLS method used in this study is appropriate. The result show that companies with higher CEO measurement index tend to have lower FRQ, at the same time, FS positively moderates the relationship between CEO and FRQ.

Our study contributes to the existing literature in several aspects: First, it provides evidence that the CEO representative composite factor affects the FRQ. Second, this evidence also demonstrates the moderating role of FS in improving the FRQ and controlling CEO behavior. Therefore, through the research results, we recommend some relevant policy implications: (1) Listed companies in Vietnam that want to improve the FRQ need to reduce the composite index measuring CEOs, by recruiting CEOs with experience as CFOs, or CEOs with MBA degrees or equivalent CPA certificates or reducing CEO rotation during the fiscal year... In addition, companies also need to increase the size of their assets to help improve the FRQ. (2) For Investors, through the composite index measuring CEO and through the FS, it is possible to identify whether the company participates in earnings management or not, as well as assess the FRQ of the company, thereby having effective investment plans.

However, the research sample is a limitation for this evidence. Since this evidence only collected from listed companies in Vietnam, the research results are not highly generalizable. In addition, although there are some factors that may affect the FRQ, they are not explored in this evidence. Therefore, the recommendation for this evidence is to enhance the research on other factors to explore in more detail the FRQ in Vietnam.

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